

Tsallis Distribution From Reaction Balance

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In (1) a Tsallis entropy is proposed such that in the limit of a certain parameter tending to 1, the expression becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. This approach makes use of the identity: $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [1 - p(\text{power } x)]/x = \ln(p)$ ((1)). Given an expression for entropy one may maximize it (with respect to p) subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ to obtain $p(e_i)$.

In this note, we argue that if one uses reaction balance, one does not need to introduce the notion of entropy or its maximization. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one has $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. We argue that reaction balance is associated with probability conservation which requires two probabilities (AND situation) hence their product. The information of a single probability, however, is taken to be e_i . In order to link $p(e_i)$ with e_i , one needs to break a product probability into a sum, thus the \ln function is used. As a result, we suggest applying the identity ((1)) directly to the expression $\ln(p) = -e_i/T$ and then generalizing by changing $x \rightarrow 0$ to x representing a nonzero number. Applying identity ((1)) to $\ln[p(e_i)p(e_j)]$ in the limit of $x \rightarrow 0$ yields ((1)) as a sum for each $p(e_i)$ and so one may generalize ((1)) with a given $p(e_i)$ to equal the information $-e_i/T$. This yields a very similar result as the maximization of entropy subject to a $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ approach. We argue, however, that the interpretation of generalizing $\ln(p(e_i))$ to Tsallis form using ((1)) may be more clear than thinking in terms of entropy.

Maximization of Entropy versus Reaction Balance

Maximization of entropy, a function of $p(e_i)$'s, with respect to $p(e_i)$ subject to a constraint is commonly used in the literature. The constraint is often $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, but $\sum_i n(e_i)$ is sometimes also included. We argue that e_i in the constraint represents the information carried by a single particle. Then $d/dp(e_i) \text{Entropy}(p(e_i))$ yields the information.

Reaction balance, on the other hand, uses conservation of energy and probability, but energy as a quantity adds while probability in an AND situation is multiplied together. If a sum equation of energy is equivalent in terms of information to a product of probabilities up to a multiplicative constant, one must find a way to break the product into a sum. The \ln function serves this purpose. This approach assumes that interactions are represented by conservation of probability which may be written as a product of functions each with a different e_i . Thus there is a certain kind of independence of probabilities present.

Tsallis Entropy

Tsallis entropy may be formulated by using identity ((1)) for $\ln(p)$ and writing an expression which in the limit of $x \rightarrow 0$ becomes $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln[p(e_i)]$. In particular, in (1) the expression is given as:

$$\text{Tsallis entropy} = 1/(q-1) \{ 1 - \sum_i p(e_i)^q \} \quad ((2))$$

Using $1 = \sum_i p(e_i)$ one has: $\sum_i p(e_i) \{1 - \sum_i p(e_i)^{q-1}\} / (q-1)$ ((3))

The expression in {} becomes in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit, $\ln(p(e_i))$ and so one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann Shannon's entropy form. This may be maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$ in order to find the Tsallis probability function $p(e_i)$.

Reaction Balance

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained using reaction balance which makes no use of the notion of entropy or its maximization. It also does not use the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i)$. The value e_i , however, does appear as it represents the information carried by a particle in a reaction. We argue that reaction balance seems to involve conservation of energy and probability, but these require two particles as this represents a physical collision which creates equilibrium. Thus:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((3b))$$

A reaction does not create or destroy probability. An issue is that ((3b)) involves a product of e_1, e_2 terms, while ((3a)) involves a sum. If the information content of ((3a)) multiplied by a constant and ((3b)) is assumed to be identical, one needs to break ((3b)) into a sum. This may be done using the \ln function. Thus:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((4))$$

The full expression of probability, however, is $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. Applying the identity ((1)) to this probability yields:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \{1 - (p(e_i)p(e_j))^x\} / x = \ln(p(e_i)p(e_j)) \quad ((5))$$

Setting $p(e_i) = \exp(a_i)$ and $p(e_j) = \exp(a_j)$ and expanding $\exp(a_i x) = 1 + a_i x$ etc to first order, then ((5)) naturally breaks into a sum of identity ((1)) for e_i and e_j . At this point, one may identify each piece with its respective information i.e. $-e_i/T$ and $-e_j/T$. If one generalizes to an x greater than 0, then:

$$\{1 - p(e_i)^x\} / x = -e_i/T \quad ((6))$$

This is the same form as obtained through maximization of entropy, creating an entropy using ((1)) with $x=q-1$, such that it yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy in the $q \rightarrow 1$ limit. (In the maximization of entropy approach, one has $\{1 - q p(e_i)^{q-1}\} / (q-1) = -e_i/T$)

What is the difference using reaction balance instead of using maximization of entropy subject to a constraint? We argue that the constraint in the problem is really the relevant information which occurs in a reaction. In a problem, it may be possible to choose many kinds of constraints, but only a special one is associated with information. For example, if $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = E_{ave}$, then another constraint is: $\sum_i e_i^2 p(e_i)$ which is related to variance.

Reaction balance instead chooses the information relevant to a collision which creates the equilibrium. It is specifically $e_i + e_j$ and $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ which are conserved and so there are no alternatives as in the constraint approach. The focus is then to break the conserved probability which uses the \ln function. In the Tsallis case, it seems that $\ln(p(e_i))$ the “sum” form of the information brought into a collision is replaced with $1/x \{1 - p(e_i)^x\}$ where x is not 0. We argue that this may have implications on the probability conservation form in a collision, because it is only in the $x \rightarrow 0$ limit that one has $p(e_i), p(e_j)$ independence i.e. product of these two creating the overall probability for a collision. It seems more direct to deal with “sum” forms of probability than with entropy which is a quantity with different interpretations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that it is typical to formulate a Tsallis entropy using an identity for $\ln(p(e_i))$, such that in the limit of a parameter tending to 1 one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann Shannon’s entropy. This may be maximized subject to a constraint which is usually taken to be $\sum_i p(e_i)$. We note that constraints are somewhat arbitrary and argue that the constraint which needs to be used is the one pertaining to the information occurring in a collision which physically creates the reaction. For example, one may have constraints using e_i, e_j etc, but in a collision it is $e_i + e_j$ which is conserved together with probability which in the MB case is $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. If a conservation of energy equation multiplied by a constant is equivalent to conservation of probability statement, then one needs to break the product of probabilities into a sum so that each may be linked to e_i, e_j etc. This may be done by the \ln function.

In the case of generalizing reaction balance to the Tsallis form, one may apply the identity ((1)) to $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. In the $x \rightarrow 0$, this breaks into a sum of ((1)) for e_i and e_j . Thus the sum form of probability in the generalized case is the identity ((1)) with x now not 0 which is set equal to $-e_i/T$ for e_i and a similar expression for $-e_j/T$ etc. Thus a very similar Tsallis result follows from working with reaction balance, although in the entropy case one has $\{1 - p^{q-1}\} / (q-1) = -e_i/T$ and in the reaction balance case $\{1 - p^{q-1}\} / (q-1) = -e_i/T$.

We argue that it may be clearer to consider the meaning of a sum form of probability in the Tsallis form instead of the entropy in the Tsallis form as entropy is physically a somewhat unusual concept. Furthermore the extremization of entropy requires a very specific constraint which we argue points to the reaction balance/information approach.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tsallis_entropy